

“Erich Fromm and the Health Coaching Identity”

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Abstract

Every interaction for the protection of well-being follows the dynamics of human relationships. Every attempt to make it exclusively technical-materialistic has underestimated the corresponding negative impacts. Health Coaching is mainly dedicated to preserving the well-being of health workers, patients and corporate organizations. He works through Pragmatic Humanism by applying maieutic in a modern key. It helps people to naturally develop their Individual Wellbeing. Its field of action is the sphere of behaviours, through a non-judgmental Presence, in a precious alliance with the individual. Some recent literature evidence points to an inconsistency between the classic approach of Coaching techniques and the need for facilitation in favour of Wellbeing. In the field of Health, the classic Executive models of Coaching Facilitation would not seem suitable for dealing with the ethical switch driven by social evolution in Healthcare Systems.

For this reason, the question relating to the roots of Health Coaching and the profound principles of an applied practical ethics that places the Person at the centre has recently arisen. Many Coaching authors and operators have developed models over time to welcome the individual and protect him from the consequences of these inconsistencies. A recent research presented at the Meeting Lab of the Italian Health Coaching Association (AIHC) held in Turin, proposed a Humanistic response to the question of the methodological roots for fully effective Coaching aimed at Individual Wellbeing. The evidence emerging from a recent philological study conducted in the field of Ethics and Social Philosophy has identified Erich Fromm as the main reference for Coaching on the side of Man and his Well-being.

Oral Communication

In this Meeting-Lab of the Italian Health Coaching Association (AIHC), a national-level event with the theme: "Health Coaching as a systemic approach in social contexts: for the empowerment and well-being of citizens", one of the topics proposed in the reports of conference, was focused on the new identity of the Health Coach and Wellness Operator.

It has been said that the time has come to bring out this identity and reclaim it. An identity that is substantial, that is based on specific themes linked to the theme of Wellbeing and that goes well beyond corporatism. We are talking about a real ontological identity of Health Coaching.

The ontological crisis of the identity of Health Coaching is based on the insufficiency of the classic model of Executive Coaching in fully inspiring the Mission of the Wellbeing Operator (AIHC, Mission and Charter of Values - <https://www.aihc.it/mission-e-carta-dei-valori/>).

To the question: Can the classic model of Executive Coaching convincingly represent the operating methods of the Health Coach? At first one might say yes. Achieving a health goal would seem to still be a problem of objective, action and performance, but are we really sure that this is the case?

Coaching as a profession was born in the world of sport.

Gallway was a professional tennis player, and after 6 months of meditation experience in the East, he returned to his homeland and noticed that his performance on the court had improved. He can't explain why. In the end he has an intuition regarding our internal dialogue. Inside us there is a Doer (an I who does) and a Teller (an I who speaks). Coaching for an eminently sporting and competitive use is born from the interaction dynamics of these two components (Gallwey, 1997)

He is later joined by a racing driver, Whitmore, who generates a coaching model: GROW (Goal, Reality, Options, Will). There is an objective, there is a possible reality with which to deal, there are options and the necessary fuel is individual will (Whitmore, 2007). To quote Erich Fromm, this is the basic scheme of intelligence-based coaching: two-dimensional coaching, which insists on a single plan established a priori. It is the pure, technical expression of problem solving and the cognitive approach. We are therefore strictly in the field of performance improvement. At this point the Business component historically intervenes, with Locke and Latham, who together publish "Goal setting & Task Performance", which decisively link Coaching techniques to the corporate world. Many other thinkers are added, such as Bandura with his self-efficacy, to work on the concept of Performance, focused eminently on performance. From here the deep and complete roots of Executive Coaching arise. Coaching is thus dedicated to achieving sporting, corporate and social performance. In a word, to the achievement of "success" commonly understood and desired. (Locke & Latham, 2017; Bandura, 1997).

The facts strongly demonstrate that the classic Performance-based Executive model, derived from the primordial Directive Coaching, does not completely satisfy the person's needs in relation to their well-being. In fact, Performance and Wellbeing do not always go together. (Dolan, 2006). Especially because, by insisting on only mono-dimensional level of sense of purpose, Executive Coaching comes into conflict with the other levels relating to individual values. Man is not just intelligent. He is also a being who uses Reason. Today we know based on Neuroscience what the effects of an internal conflict are between the achievement of socially considered Success and the failure to satisfy one's personal well-being (Gazzaniga, 2020; Dolan, 1992). This conflict is sometimes so deep and so violent, that at different times and independently, several authors have had the intuition of being able and having to create some correction in the classic model of Executive Coaching as personal development, to protect the person from possible negative consequences of the conflict itself and move it, beyond the megatrends, towards a preferable Future (Voros, 2017).

The singular prerogative that all these authors have in common is the use of the approach to Values and their meaning for the individual. This trend is confirmed and described in a non-specific way as a phenomenon detected in the UK healthcare system as "Ethical Coaching". (Iordanou, 2017).

Let's see briefly how these scholars realize that a conflict can exist between the achievement of socially considered Success and one's personal well-being.

Simon Dolan, a Canadian work psychologist, understands that Personal Wellbeing and Organizational Wellbeing are two strongly connected elements. He realizes that many chronic pathologies are generated due to a value misalignment between the value system of the person and that of the company. This is how Coaching by Values was born, with the aim of generating a healthy development of performance while respecting individual well-being (Dolan, 2006).

Richard Barrett, a management engineer in the banking system, similarly detects a distorting phenomenon in the corporate system which he later describes as "cultural entropy". Values that are potentially toxic and are instead considered necessary by the management system in the current corporate culture generate conflict, dispersion of energy and chaos. Creates the Values Barrett Centre to generate a business transformation that embraces group and personal values into a system that is healthy and sustainable (Barrett, 2012).

Robert Dilts, in his book “Beliefs”, presents his NLP technique based on logical levels, as a continuation of Maslow's humanistic psychology thinking (Maslow, 1968). He also sees the importance of protecting the individual from "success at all costs", verifying whether the final objective, often desired from the outside and apparently desired by the subject, is in line with the system of values, beliefs, ability, will and means of the individual. It does more. It builds a real "ecological check" of the objective, in order to predict the sustainability of the final objective achieved, in this case, by the client. (Dilts, 2012).

This conflict between Performance and Wellbeing is so profound and so violent that it led these authors to have the intuition that they could and should create some modification to the classic model of Executive Coaching. They propose an alternative personal development with a sense of purpose, therefore three-dimensional, to protect the person from possible negative consequences of the internal conflict itself, due to the pressing demand for performance as an end in itself or, even worse, based on the purpose of others.

To finally arrive at a modern thought that truly puts the individual at the centre, we must arrive at the turning point promoted by Seligman (2012), at the 2000 World Congress of Psychology, where Positive Psychology gave further strength to the importance of man as individual and the positive effect of enhancing its qualities.

Specifically, Appreciative Coaching has been added to this new movement (Orem et al., 2007) which places emphasis on the positive elements of the person, through the five principles:

Constructionist > the positive history of the individual
Simultaneity > the instant evocative power of powerful questions
Anticipatory > imagining a preferable Future influences the present
Positive > in line with Seligman and Berne, positive reinforcement generates creativity
Poetic > each of us has a story to tell: each of us is a story.

This approach to Coaching acts as a filter on the Coach's speech in the relationship with the person, without however going into the merits of its profound meaning. Like previous approaches, it is substantially empirical and based on practical evidence, lacking a philosophical, methodological, sociological, phenomenological connection. It is the limit of a super specialized society organized for specific skills, functions and competencies.

These testimonies reported so far are among the most significant to underline how tangible the limit of the Sports-Executive Coaching model is in the Wellbeing field, as it was born and implemented. All this opens up a reflection on how Health Coaching, similarly, must consequently start from a completely different point of view from the approach of classic Executive Coaching. None of the classic Coaching methodologists examines the central point of the essence of Health Coaching from an ontological, systematic and philosophical point of view:

- Is there the possibility of generating an objective humanistic approach to personal development?
- What mechanisms can generate well-being within the social system?
- How can we help the person to develop in a healthy way, avoiding an approach that is too based on "performance"?

Today we present, for the first time, the observation of a profound link between Erich Fromm's thought and the ethical and also practical foundation of Health Coaching, quoting this phrase of his:

“The strength of impulses towards happiness and health are part of man's natural baggage”

Fromm was an inspiration to many thinkers, psychologists and welfare workers who succeeded him who, directly or indirectly, were influenced by the undisputed father of social psychology. With his work and his publications, he revealed psychoanalytic concepts, making them philosophically and socially available for a specific reason: The Well-being of Man. In his work of social criticism, he effectively made psychoanalysis secular, revealing its implications.

To understand how deeply Fromm respected individual freedom, he consciously decided not to write psychotherapy manuals. For this reason, he has often been criticized and rejected by the most orthodox circles of psychoanalysis. In reality he left his successors and students free to dynamically develop his thinking. Which, reconstructing the last 40 years since his death, has punctually occurred. Many have drawn from his insights. What he left us is the Methodology, the key concepts of Practice that we can rightly cite today as inspiring not only Positive Psychology, but also Health Coaching and Wellbeing. In the pages of his essays we find concepts and tools developed subsequently. By carefully reading his works, we can easily recognize some surprising intuitions and anticipations.

Here are some examples of Fromm's genius and accuracy (Fromm, 1947).

the principle of scarcity (Cialdini, 2006):

*"The body's unsatisfied needs generate tension, the removal of which gives satisfaction.
Lack itself is the basis of satisfaction..."*

exchange in abundance (see – websites)

*"While even in animals there is energy in abundance, which expresses itself in play,
the realm of abundance is essentially a human phenomenon...
Productive love is a phenomenon of superabundance,
and the ability to enjoy it is testimony to human maturity.
Joy and happiness are concomitant factors of productive love."*

and even the famous Coaching equation:

Performance = Potential – Interferences

Declined like this:

"healing means removing the obstacles that prevent these impulses from being effective"

Considering that based on the observations of Barrett and Dolan, much of the malaise derives from moral distress (Borg, 2006), only the genius of Erich Fromm seems to give a methodological and systematic explanation of this phenomenon. His approach as a populariser of psychoanalysis understood as an instrument of social, philosophical and political progress is able to fully satisfy a question which, by its prerogative, requires an in-depth and objective analysis of the ethical and moral question.

Some of Erich Fromm's central themes that declare the profound connection between Ethics and Well-being can be found again in "A Man for Himself" (1947):

*"...To know what is good for man, we need to know his nature.
Humanistic ethics is the science applied to the art of living,
based on the theoretical "science of man..."*

*.... The art of living, the sense of purpose of man's life,
must be understood as the unfolding of his powers according to the laws of nature...*

*According to objective humanistic ethics,
the failure of productive maturation is a moral failure....*

*Violating the forces directed in the direction of life in any human being
has repercussions on ourselves.
So, our own growth and happiness and energy
are based on respect for these forces.
This fact is a condition of life and health"*

The ethical and practical foundation of Health Coaching is based on these and other concepts of Erich Fromm's thought. Only conscious support for the development of a person's natural productivity can be effective in developing well-being. It is necessary to free the space of the session from influences of interests and dynamics external to the person. The deepening of the person's real sense of purpose becomes the fundamental and distinctive cornerstone of Health Coaching.

To cite other significant reasons, I like to recall here at least 3 key aspects of Fromm's thoughts on Wellbeing: ETHICS, ART AND PRACTICE.

ETHICS - Fromm is central to Wellbeing Methodology due to his Humanistic position. He strongly maintains that well-being is produced within man and not sought outside of him. Fromm demonstrates, through what he defines as Objective Humanistic Ethics, the profoundly Beneficial nature of Man and his prerogative to tend towards his self-realization and happiness and well-being. It corresponds exactly to the Health Coach's real trust in the means and possibilities of his interlocutor.

Even this alone would be enough to recognize the root of the Principles of Health Coaching in Fromm, especially for the methodological rigor with which he asserts this position in his essays, and "A Man for Himself" is the unsurpassed pillar of this treatment ethics and philosophical-social.

ART - There is a second subsidiary reason that makes it a methodological point of reference for both the Health Coach and the Person. Fromm talks about what an Art is, understood as a human (and humanistic) profession. It can be the Art of Living for the Person, it can be the Art of facilitation for the Health Coach, but also any other type of productive activity that is perceived to be of great interest, as an opportunity for personal growth... (Fromm, 1963).

Each art, he claims, must be able to have 4 prerogatives:

- the **supreme interest** in Art itself
- **discipline** in practicing the Art
- **concentration** (or *conscious deliberation*) in practicing it (anticipating here both the concept of Mindfulness and Flow State)
- **patience** in knowing that Art needs time to be fruitful.

Imagine what effect a reflection dedicated to these 4 points of the Art (of Living?) could have during a Health Coaching session:

- how interested are you in this specific activity?
- how and how much do you dedicate yourself daily? How do you ensure continuity?
- how and to what extent do you immerse yourself completely and productively in the activity?
- how much do you know how to wait for the necessary times, experiences and learning, appreciating them?

This is already in the example of practical application of Fromm's Objective Humanistic Ethics. Let's see some others.

PRACTICE

Among the many pieces of evidence, I want to mention the clearest and most significant one of how much the current approach to individual well-being is rooted in Fromm's thought and how the latter is indisputably related to the identity of the Health Coach.

Fromm argues that the positive shift in character is productivity, understood as the ability to develop one's human potential for the purpose of personal happiness. He is the first to write such clear concepts strongly linked to Health Coaching, or he does so in the second half of the 1940s (Fromm, 1947)

It also clarifies that personal happiness is not necessarily the same as "social success" (Fromm, 1961). And this watershed definitively determines a different identity between Executive Coaching (success, performance) and Health Coaching (development of one's well-being through empowerment). They are two completely different points of view that provide separate positions and identities. This is where I find the limit in identifying Health Coaching as a simple branch derived from Sport, Life, Executive.

Coming to the point, the two concepts Ethics and Practice are often perceived on different levels. Ethics as a general principle, which dictates the rules, Practice as a life lived that has an effective impact on the world and on personal life. Fromm, however, produces a synthesis of these two components as two sides of the same coin, especially with regard to the world of individual well-being and therefore of Health Coaching. Fromm demonstrates admirably that Ethics and Practice are actually the same thing, because through choices and actions, they are linked to the dynamics of Values and therefore to Morality (the rules) (Fromm, 1947, 1961, 1963)

And here a world opens up.

Among the practical tools that we can derive from Fromm's thought, there are certainly some valuable dialectical polarities, the result of an elicitation of the sense of personal purpose as opposed to that of the social context.

We could call these polarities linguistic distinctions, according to the model of ontological-transformational coaching (Echeverria, 2017). Setting up a path of awareness by facilitating the switch of beliefs from one polarity to another is one of the most powerful tools of transformational coaching:

Success Vs Happiness

Those who follow success and money too much consciously renounce happiness

Activity Vs Productivity

You can be very active without being productive.

Were your last 5 years of life a progressive growth in awareness?

Or were they repeating the same year 5 times?

Profit vs Produce

Exploit others or develop others

Power Vs Faith

Centralize control or delegate with confidence

Power over Vs Power of

The difference between dominance=alienating and ability=freeing

Intelligence vs Reason

A two-dimensional reality (problem solver) and a three-dimensional one, which includes, in addition to objective and measurement, also a sense of purpose

These distinctions can be very useful in supporting a healthy lifestyle that produces well-being.

If we look closely in hindsight, Fromm is the natural source of many other subsequent intuitions. A truly very important one, which generates change and humanistic transformation, is the dynamic conception of the social character. According to Fromm, the individual prerogative of the person is fluid and can express itself in a functional or dysfunctional way. There are no good or bad personality profiles: there are profiles that can express themselves in a constructive or destructive way. It is the concept that we subsequently find in the "positive shift" of the so-called "drives" in Eric Berne's Transactional Analysis (1973) (Stewart & Joines, 1987). He too, by identifying behavioural models, understands their negative or positive dynamic capacity. All this closely resembles the "productive behaviour" of the various social styles described by Fromm. Each of us has a personality trait that can express itself in a functional or dysfunctional way. An interesting idea of social character traits that could be useful and very current in a Health Coaching session is to work on the productive components:

Receptive > accepting things from others > following authority

Exploitative > take > lead others

Hoarding > saving > being alone

Marketing > exchange > assert oneself

Working on the critical tension between

Necrophilia-destructiveness > **Biophilia**-productivity

The misalignment of values in society and companies - Fromm's study describes and predicts the negative impacts of a misalignment of values, indicating possible solutions. It identifies moral failure as the main cause of individual pain and indicates in great detail what the true task of society in general and, in its small way, of a company in particular should be:

“Society can be organized in such a way that the norms necessary for its survival conflict with the norms necessary for the fullest development of its members.

This is especially true in societies where privileged groups dominate or exploit the rest of the population...

The contradiction between immanent social ethics and universal ethics will be reduced and will tend to disappear to the same extent that society becomes truly human, that is, it will take care of the full human development of all its members”

In the meantime, taking care of the well-being of the person victim of the conflict of interest of the social ethical system will be a specific and essential task of Health Coaching.

In summary, Fromm argues that the positive shift in character is productivity, understood as the ability to develop one's human potential for the purposes of personal happiness. He is the first to write such clear concepts strongly linked to the Health Coach Vision. It also clarifies that personal happiness does not necessarily coincide with "social success" (Fromm, 1987). Based on the analysis of the social context, it predicts what would occur (and is very clear today): a different methodological basis between Executive Coaching (success, performance) and Health Coaching (development of one's well-being through empowerment). They are two different points of view that foresee divergent positions and purposes. Today we must be able to take control of these two trends in light of their convergence and synergy.

Thanks to this pragmatic rereading of Fromm, today Health Coaching can realign its approach to regenerate its facilitation techniques and partnership with the Doctor and the Patient. This will allow a natural empowerment of the person, in light of a new Humanistic Transformation that is increasingly emerging as a synthesis of the Evolution of Man.

All this rightly makes Erich Fromm the methodological inspirer of Health Coaching. He is the source of the identity of every humanistic operator: the one who supports the ethical position of the client, for his well-being. This inspiration fully corresponds to the spirit of the AIHC Association, which welcomes all the professionals dedicated to personal well-being, in a great alliance.

*"Humanistic ethics may well postulate happiness and joy as its fundamental virtues.
In doing so, he alludes to the most difficult task that man can set himself:
the full development of one's productivity"*

In conclusion, I can say, in this AIHC Lab Meeting, that in Erich Fromm we have not only recognized and today accredited the identity of the Health Coach, but also that of all Wellness Operators. We can all rightly refer to this great Humanist as our ethical and methodological inspirer. And this must fill us with pride, for our nascent professional identity, and, above all, to give value to him, who planted the seed of it, with trust in Man.

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